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Perceptions and Experiences of Postgraduate Students of Educational Management vis-a-vis Academic Jealousy

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ABSTRACT

This study intends to reveal perceptions and experiences pertaining to postgraduate students of educational management related to the concept of academic jealousy. The study is a qualitative one designed with the understanding of Phenomenology. The participants consist of 10 students who had received and were receiving postgraduate education in the area of educational management. 1 of them is an academic, 6 are teachers, 1 is a manager in a non-governmental organization, and 2 are managers in public schools. Four semi-structured questions were asked during the focus group interview held via Google Meet. Content analysis was executed to analyze the data. Through the findings, it was obvious jealousy was experienced in academic/scientific publication processes and in the context of managerial duties/promotions in academic trajectories and through the competition between individuals. Academic jealousy seemingly harmed the involved individual, and individuals became isolated on account of academic competition. Addedly, academic jealousy had relevance to the individual's personality traits, rearing, the culture of the related organization, age, and workload. It was found the feeling of academic jealousy has a complex being and should be managed well. Consequently, academic jealousy carries the potential to harm individuals and higher education institutions. Academic leaders need to take individual psychological characteristics into account in their management style knowing when to intervene in team conflicts, create opportunities for learning, provide coaching and mentoring. Respect and concern for others, positive reinforcement, and open dialogue will be effective herbicide against envy weeds in academia. These key actions will help emerging researchers grow in a more supportive environment and minimize the devastating side effects of jealousy.

Keywords: Academic jealousy, educational management, postgraduate education, postgraduate perceptions.

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Introduction

It is observed academic structures, which are expected to be entities relatively more isolated from emotions to make (more) room for rational and scientific thought, are inevitably surrounded by emotions. The environments in which and through which educational activities are carried out, the academic performance of the immediate parties viz. learners and teachers are frequently discussed (Seibert et al., 2017) and they welcome numerous emotions and emotional states (Burić, Sorić & Penezić, 2016). Jealousy is one of the first amongst the said feelings, and expressed as one that individuals gain the most familiarity through their personal experiences since they get involved in several processes both as the subject and the object. It can herein be noted that the notion of jealousy, which is portrayed as a human emotion in a fair number of different fields such as Literature and the discipline of Psychology, has found a place in the works and studies produced throughout the course of history.

When it comes to academia, to combat with fierce academic ambitions that distance individuals from humanity (Sterne, 2011) today, certain efforts are being made and "slowing down attempts" are witnessed that are constructed with a view to eliminating competition. Howbeit, the philosophy of "publish or perish" continues to be effective. Undoubtedly, this causes the concept of jealousy to manifest itself strongly in academic circles, where individuals directly/indirectly conduct research for humans. In this way, it will make sense to investigate jealousy by placing it on an academic ground to see an up-to-date plane of what is happening in the axis in question. Performing this, primarily through students enrolled in a graduate program will make it possible to evaluate the lived experiences closely such as identity development and the perceived "depression", the desire to gain a place in the academy, and academic rise (Hemmings, Hill & Sharp, 2013) whilst making it easier to better understand the phenomenon within the framework of social sciences, an area with unique dynamics where loneliness and stress might come up (Atalay, 2018). Doing so may shed light on difficulties graduate students face, efforts, and academic motivation (Hegarty, Brasco & Lu, 2012).

Theoretical Framework and A Review of Literature

To examine the phenomenon of academic jealousy in a more refined way and among academic groups, it is deemed crucial to position the referent accurately within the other academic emotional states by delving into the available studies. When we explore in detail the accumulated research in the field, the existence of an academic emotion concept set stands out first. This concept set includes feelings of satisfaction, hopelessness, anxiety, anger, and pride (Pekrun et al., 2002). As it is understood, this set formed by academic emotions is monitored in a versatile way. The labyrinth metaphor is now used when talking about the steps of a ladder for academic career development (Pason, 2011), drawing attention to that academic feelings and emotions may become so complex. In fact, Laurencelle and Scallan (2018) underpinned the self-efficacy status of students attending graduate programs is constantly changing with numerous emotions e.g., belonging, perseverance, and success.

It can be an easy orientation for researchers to isolate academic emotions, which entail a highly complicated integrity, from the large and painful discussions in the field (Lindquist et al., 2013) and examine them in two main tracks. Academic emotions are more specific to the results to be obtained, such as disappointment and hope arising from both success and failure also italicizing academic processes and depict the feelings about the progress, to wit, taking delight in working (Ketonen et al., 2017). The positive or negative burden of these emotions was recorded

(Linnenbrink & Pintrich, 2002) as a reason for being active or passive (Kleine et al., 2005). Here, academic emotions often take shape with social connections, experiences, bonds, and communications (Pekrun et al., 2002). Conceptualizations that are the subject of academic studies along with academic feelings (e.g., motivation Elliot, 2006; contexts—e.g., Harmon-Jones et al., 2016) are the ones that stem from social structures. Without doubt, the feeling(s) of academic jealousy should be approached with the premise that its social scope is vast. Academic jealousy, in which the individual gets exposed to an academic comparison with the others, causes that individual to consider their *raison d'être* under a collective roof.

There are studies in the literature that examine academic emotions with quantitative paradigms. To illustrate, Pekrun et al. (2011) found that they created the first comprehensive tool to measure students' multiple feelings of achievement through the Academic Emotions Questionnaire (AEQ) and determined that the sense of achievement was related to motivation, strategies, self-regulation, and performance. Govaerts and Grégoire (2008) with the Academic Emotions Scale (AES) they developed, and this scale is a French self-report questionnaire assessing six emotions in the context of school learning. These emotions are enjoyment, hope, pride, anxiety, shame, and frustration. Trigwell, Ellis, and Han (2012) with the help of the Students' Emotion Experiences Scale (SEEI) they brought to the area have conducted research carrying a similar scope. As a result of the research, both the experience of more positive emotions and the adoption of a deeper approach are associated with higher achievement scores. That being said, the idea that academic emotions, which are subjective and contextual, can be scrutinized in purely quantitative ways is misleading. Mattsson, Hailikari and Parpala (2020) have put forth it is of utmost importance to study these by preserving their originality in qualitative ways. Rowe, Fitness and Wood (2015) examined university students' and lecturers' perceptions of positive emotions in the learning process. As a result of the research, the themes associated with five positive emotions were revealed and the views of the participants were compared.

Dwelling upon the nature of academic jealousy can become more appropriate via accessing the foundations of the concept in a chronicle. The "Social Comparison Theory," which Festinger (1954) brought to the field has an eminent place in this sense. According to this theory, individuals make their comparisons and gain beliefs about what they own, that is, abilities, skills, and capacities, especially in the absence of criteria by which they can subject themselves to objective comparisons. Following the Social Comparison Theory, Messick and McClintock (1968) stated with the "Social Value Orientation Theory" that individuals establish a rapport with others taking a utilitarian stance. "Competitive Arousal Theory" (Ku, Malhotra, & Murnighan, 2005; Ku, Galinsky, & Murnighan, 2006) is another theory. Henderson and Milstein (1996) noted academic emotions are connected to phenomena such as academic awareness and academic perseverance. In this context, the aim of the study is to reveal perceptions and experiences pertaining to postgraduate students of educational management related to the concept of academic jealousy.

Importance of the Study

It is shared by many that the concept of jealousy is hardly addressed by the researchers in the bulk of literature of Türkiye (e.g., Gunalan, 2019). Delving into academic jealousy in universities will help closely observe the situations, which are accepted as bases for the production and dissemination of accurate information (Ozdemir & Erdem, 2020). Postgraduate students are the participants of this study since there is no research focusing on the perceptions and experiences of postgraduate students in educational management toward academic jealousy. Furthermore, there

is no undergraduate degree of educational management in Turkey because it was repealed towards the end of the 1990s. Therefore, the postgraduate students were chosen as the study group.

The Purpose of the Study and Research Questions

The purpose of the study is to reveal perceptions and experiences pertaining to postgraduate students of educational management related to the concept of academic jealousy. In this context, the research questions are presented below:

1. How are the 'academic feelings' of postgraduate students in the field of educational administration in their postgraduate education processes?
2. What are the competition/jealousy situations that postgraduate students in the field of educational administration are exposed/subject to during their postgraduate education?
3. How are the academic/professional career plans of postgraduate students in the field of educational administration in the short, medium and long term?
4. What is the relationship between the career plans of the postgraduate students in the field of educational administration and the academic feelings they experience and the situations of competition/jealousy?

Method

Pattern of the Research

The present research is a qualitative study designed with Phenomenology (Abulad, 2007). Phenomenological research focuses on any lived experience of participants related to a phenomenon (Yuksel & Yildirim, 2015). Creswell (2012) also remarked that phenomenological research depicts the common meaning for lots of people of their lived experiences about a concept or phenomenon. In this context, the perceptions and experiences of the students who received postgraduate education in educational management and who had experiences with academic jealousy were analyzed in depth.

Participants

The participants consist of 10 students who had received and were receiving postgraduate education in the area of educational management in state and foundation universities. Bearing in mind that making informed decisions as regards sampling is indeed critical to enhancing the overall quality of research (Suri, 2011), the criteria sampling method (Patton, 2002), one of the purposeful sampling types, was resorted to in the forming of the study group, and "being a state university student/graduate, being a foundation university student/graduate" was determined as the criterion. Although opinions about the number of participants differs in the literature, this number usually varies between 4 and 10 people (Cokluk, Yilmaz & Oguz, 2011). The demographic attributes are given in Table 1.

Table 1. Demographic attributes of the participants

Variables	Groups	f	%
Gender	Female	4	40
	Male	6	60
Age	24	1	10
	28	2	20
	32	1	10
	34	1	10
	35	1	10
	38	1	10
	39	1	10
	41	1	10
Type of University where Postgraduate Education is Received	State	5	50
	Foundation	5	50
Undergraduate Program Completed	Science Teaching	1	10
	Philosophy	1	10
	Primary School Teaching	1	10
	Primary School teaching and Philosophy teaching	1	10
	Turkish Language and Literature	1	10
	Primary Education Mathematics Teaching	1	10
	English Language and Literature	1	10
	English Language Teaching	3	30
	Graduated Postgraduate Program	Educational Management (with thesis, completed)	5
Education management (with thesis, ongoing)		3	30
Educational Sciences (non-thesis, completed)		1	10
Educational Management (without thesis, ongoing)		1	10
Occupation	Academic	1	10
	Teacher	6	60
	Manager (NGO)	1	10
	Administrator (Public school)	2	20
Professional Seniority	4 years 6 months	1	10
	5 years	2	20
	9 years	1	10
	10 years	2	20
	14 Years	1	10
	16 years	1	10
19 Years	2	20	

The demographic information of the students receiving postgraduate education in the field of Educational Management can be expressed as follows: 4 (40%) are female, and 6 (60%) are male; 1 (10%) is 24 years old, 2 (20%) are 28 years old, 1 (10%) is 32 years old, 1 (10%) is 34

years old, 1 (10%) is 35 years old, 1 (10%) is 38 years old, 1 (10%) is 39 years old, 1 (10%) is 41 years old, and 1 (10%) is 42 years old.

Respecting the type of university where postgraduate education is received, 5 (50%) are public universities, and 5 (50%) foundation universities; as for the graduated undergraduate program, 1 (10%) graduated from Science Teaching, 1 (10%) graduated from Philosophy, 1 (10%) graduated from Classroom Teaching, 1 (10%) graduated from both Classroom Teaching and Philosophy teaching, 1 (10%) graduated from Turkish Language and Literature, 1 (10%) graduated from Primary School Mathematics Teaching, 1 (10%) graduated from English Language and Literature, and 3 (30%) graduated from English Language Teaching. Regarding the graduated master's program, 5 (50%) of the participants graduated from an Educational Management postgraduate program with a thesis; 1 (10%) graduated from an Educational Sciences postgraduate program without a thesis, and 3 (30%) graduated from an Educational Management postgraduate program with thesis and 1 (10%) graduated from an Educational Management postgraduate program without thesis.

When it comes to the profession of the participants, 1 (10%) of them is an academic, 6 (60%) are teachers, 1 (10%) is a manager in a non-governmental organization, and 2 (20%) are managers in public schools; and with respect to professional seniority, 1 (10%) has 4 years and 6 months, 2 (20%) has 5 years, 1 (10%) has 9 years, 2 (20%) has 10 years, 1 (10%) has 14 years, 1 (10%) has 16 years, and 2 (20%) has 19 years of professional seniority.

Data Collection

The participating individuals were asked seven demographic questions posed to arrive at information pertaining to gender, age, type of university where they received postgraduate education and also to the graduated undergraduate program, graduated postgraduate program, and lastly to professional seniority through Google Forms designed by the researchers. Four semi-structured questions, which reached their final versions in light of what the 3 field experts shared for feedback purposes, were asked during the focus group interview held via Google Meet. The reason behind resorting to focus group discussions was that they help discover “the real feelings and issues that provide richer than personal interviews or surveys, because the dynamics of a group lead to more developed answers.” (Basnet, 2018: 82).

Data Analysis

The focus group interview was recorded with the consent of all the participants, then the recording was transcribed by one of the researchers. Afterwards, the other researcher first went through these transcriptions and carry out a content analysis using the NVIVO qualitative analysis software. Content analysis is oftentimes recruited to comprehend any content of messages such as text, image, symbol or audio data (Gheyle & Jacobs, 2017). Codes such as P1 and P5 were given to each participant to disguise real names to abide by ethical concerns. When the opinions of the participants were analyzed, six themes were obtained: "Factors affecting academic plans," "Academic jealousy in varying contexts," "The nature of academic jealousy," "The results of academic jealousy," "The basics of academic jealousy" and "Suggestions for academic jealousy." Under the first theme “Factors affecting academic plans”, neutral direction, positive direction and negative direction as sub-themes were reached. Another theme was "the results of academic jealousy." The sub-themes that came up with this theme were: "no academic jealousy," "in the positive direction," and "in the negative direction." Under the other themes, no sub-themes were reached but reached codes and all the codes were presented in the findings in detail.

Trustworthiness

To ensure the validity of the data obtained, the detailed description method was made use of. The statements were presented directly in their original form in the findings section. As for validity of the translations, one researcher who is a translator translated the transcriptions later to be checked by the other researcher. Following this, the translated transcriptions were sent to another translator, who is also a colleague and faculty member in Educational Sciences, and a cross-check was realized (McMillan & Schumacher, 2006).

For the sorting out of codes and themes, the replies were gone through by the researchers. In this direction, the reliability formula introduced by Miles and Huberman (1994) was exploited to calculate the inter-coder reliability of the research. Whereas there was a consensus between the first encoder and the researcher in 33 codes, a disagreement was spotted in 4 codes. When the calculation was made according to the given formula, the reliability was found as %89. Furthermore, there was a consensus between the second encoder and the researcher in 28 codes, yet a disagreement was detected in 9 codes. When the calculation was made according to the relevant formula, the reliability of the research was found to be %76. The reliability calculation exceeding 70% is considered reliable (Miles and Huberman, 1994). In this frame of reference, the acknowledged coding is recognized as reliable (Creswell & Plano Clark, 2007).

2.6. Ethics Committee Approval Process

To attain data, an application was made to the Scientific Research and Publication Ethics Committee of Muş Alparslan University of Türkiye, and the research was found to be following ethical principles with decision No 3 made at the meeting No 1 dated 04 January 2022.

Findings

The opinions seemed to gather under six themes: "Factors affecting academic plans," "Academic jealousy in varying contexts," "The nature of academic jealousy," "The results of academic jealousy," "The basics of academic jealousy" and "Suggestions for academic jealousy." For the saturation of the themes, the opinions of the participants were analyzed under the frame of the relevant interview question within the context of the content analysis and coded accordingly. Each of the interview questions were converted to themes. Since the main aim was not to make comparisons but to unearth the relevant experiences of the participants in parallel with the research paradigm we pursued, we attempted to share the lived experiences in depth as much as possible.

Factors Affecting Academic Plans

The first theme determined from the focus group interview is "factors affecting academic plans." The sub-themes are: "in the neutral direction," "in the positive direction," and "in the negative direction." Under the sub-theme of "in a neutral direction," "the attitude of the faculty member did not affect my academic plans" code; under the sub-theme of "in a positive direction," "the support of my family directed me to the academy," "my belief in education familiarized me with the academy," "the approach of the faculty members, positively affected my academic plans" codes were detected. Under the sub-theme of "in a negative direction," "jealousy and grouping alienated me from the academy," "the approach of the faculty member negatively affected my academic plans," "politics and networking alienated me from the academy," "seeing the success of the academy as worthless, alienated me from the academy," "not giving importance to information, alienated me from the academy," "my characteristics, alienated me from the academy" and "lack of financial gain, alienated me from the academy" codes were figured out. These are demonstrated in Table 2 below.

Table 2. Factors affecting academic plans

Opinions	
<p>1. Sub-Theme: Neutral Direction</p>	<p>Opinion</p>
<p>The attitudes of the faculty member did not affect my academic plans.</p>	<p>“...I criticized the professor in the class without hurting his feelings, but this caused a problem. Then things got even worse; we ended up in the court. I was sentenced to reprimand. My master's degree extended for two years. I have experienced all these; I said, ‘there will always be such people in life,’ so my determination did not increase, or my motivation did not decrease. ”</p>
<p>2. Sub-Theme: Positive Direction</p>	<p>Opinions</p>
<p>My parents' support led me to the academy.</p>	<p>It was much easier for me to get accepted to ‘.....’ (here the name of the university is revealed so it is intentionally left blank). I took the exams, and I was accepted. I think my family provided me with lots of encouragement during this process. Because we have a tradition of constantly embracing education and self-education in the family, I realized this later and asked the question: ‘So, were these really my independent choices, or was it something that all families impose on their children?’ ”</p>
<p>My faith in education urged me to be the academy.</p>	<p>"You have only one life, where would it be better to spend it? Running a business and getting rich and making money or something? I am still on this path since it is more valuable to leave something mentally, intellectually, and educationally meaningful. "</p>
<p>The approach of the faculty members positively affected my academic plans.</p>	<p>" ‘We have a supportive environment here; we will have our postgraduate degree from here’ we started talking amongst peers. From that point of view, that support acts as an extremely important parameter in the academy for people to continue. I could have left, I could never have joined the academy, I could not have applied for a master's degree after that interview, but I had a supportive environment; people were encouraged, and they wanted to do something more.”</p>
<p>3. Sub-Theme: Negative Direction</p>	<p>Opinions</p>
<p>Jealousy and grouping have alienated me from the academy.</p>	<p>“You live the life once, so it would not appeal to you to give 15 hours of your 24 hours to the academic world, particularly as a result of this jealousy, and consider the environment is not peaceful. “I think people get tired and not turn to academia, and I am of the opinion that unqualified people; people who attend with an easier network will also prepare unqualified works, and I believe the country will be damaged owing to this. “ “I listen to stories of jealousy, clichés, groupings, yes, I witness these, I feel as if I do not belong here, nor to the academic studies in this country, I feel like I do not belong at all... It led to such a change in my career plan. ” “I do not know who the jury will be when I apply for an associate professorship position in the future. After all, the Council of Higher Education is assigning these members of the jury, and when it comes to teachers who are grouped with such thoughts, ‘Will I be able to attend, even if I attend, these groupings and schism may even turn out to be mobbing afterward.’ Upon seeing such things, my motivation for academic career planning decreases. I am not sure whether I can endure all these.”</p>
<p>The faculty member's approach negatively affected my academic plans.</p>	<p>"I chose to attend the course of a lecturer, and when we started the course, when he saw that I was the 81st person, not the 80th person, because he was a very grumpy lecturer, he asked ‘Why are you here?’, made other comments and he wanted to remove my name from the course. One less student would be better for him. We went to his office, and I had my name removed from the course and I saw him laughing for the first time, and he laughed because someone had just left the course. I went out, called my friends and said, ‘I do not want to be like this; should I ever want to become an academic one day, change my mind, if possible...’ ”</p>

My friend and I applied together to the postgraduate program of a foundation university, but we encountered an extremely rude, disrespectful environment. I mean, it was crystal clear that we were not wanted. As a matter of fact, even if we got a successful result, my friend and I would not apply; we did not matriculate. We said, 'We cannot have a master's degree in this way.'

"When I got accepted to the university where I worked, one professor asked me what I was working on, I said it was Critical Pedagogy, and he said, 'I do not accept the subjects you study; you have no place here'. I was shocked hearing this in the first step of my career, of course, it actually meant a few steps back.

Politics and networking have alienated me away from the academy.	<p>"I wanted to educate myself and become an academic. Nonetheless, with networking and politics, I thought, one can resist for a certain period, but would certainly be demoralized at some point."</p> <p>"Your background and your teaching are ignored. When you utter, 'I am doing a doctorate,' people say, 'You do it with the help of money or with the help of your political connections.' It was also mirrored in publications and plagiarism acts. Some gets their theses written. There is now a perception in public just as you have a seat there thanks to your power. Inescapably, this lowers your motivation. "</p>
Success is recognized as worthless and has alienated me from the academy.	<p>"...My brother really wanted to be an academic, and he had a bad influence on me. He came first in the ALES (academic personnel and postgraduate education entrance exam) in Türkiye. He graduated from METU (Middle East Technical University) in the first place. They did not give him a chance to get his master's degree; he got his master's and doctorate degrees in US. He has been living there for 20 years. He is not intending to come, and he does not really want to come. He always gives examples of academic jealousy, envy, and alike. "</p>
The lack of emphasis on gaining knowledge has alienated me from the academy.	<p>"I applied for a master's degree, and the interviewer asks a question or something he does not know about. He is confused because he is 60-70 years old and thinks he has defeated you by doing that, but you are disappointed, even in academic interviews, knowledge is not important; hard work is not appreciated."</p>
My characteristics and the incompatibility of expectations in the academy have alienated me from the academy.	<p>"Should I continue my academic life, I have to devote my life to it thinking that I cannot go for non-quality publications just to receive a title. I need to spend most of my time and effort on this subject?. And my mind has not changed."</p>
The lack of financial gain alienated me from the academy.	<p>"I have never thought of becoming an academic. I just like reading. I like to improve myself. There is not enough money for academics, you can get a position, nevertheless the salary is not adequate. You see primary school graduates, people others tend to look down on, they earn 30-40 thousand of liras in a month. "</p>

These hint at that the attitudes of the faculty members encountered did not affect the academic plans of some. The range of these views was worthy of examination.

It is noteworthy that family support and belief in the value of education positively affect academic plans. Also, it was implied besides organizational behaviors such as jealousy and grouping, political relations and connections had adverse effects. The reduction of academic achievement, considering gaining knowledge as an insignificant outcome, the incompatibility of personal characteristics and academic expectations, and the lack of financial gain were other factors impeding academic plans.

Academic Jealousy in Varying Contexts

The second theme reached is "academic jealousy in varying contexts." The codes are: "jealousy in the academic context," "jealousy in the context of a comparison between faculty

members," "jealousy in the context of academic publication," "jealousy in the context of managerial duty/promotion within the academy," "jealousy in the context of academic incentive allowance," "jealousy in the context of the relatively wide academic environment" and "jealousy in the context of favoritism by faculty members." The participants' opinions, themes, and codes are displayed in Table 3.

Table 3. Academic jealousy in varying contexts

Codes	Opinions
Jealousy in an academic context	<p>"There is much competition for those who graduated in our period; everyone wants to be elected by doing more than the others. I don't know; many people around me want to go abroad. Again, it is a situation brought about by the school. For instance, I think being jealous about friends going abroad for postgraduate or doctorate studies may be counted within the framework of academic jealousy. "</p> <p>"Friends who are thinking of switching to a master's degree with a thesis (from the non-thesis program) do not share their homework with peers; they talk to the professor and receive the details and feedback, but they do not tell us these. I mean, you are just a non-thesis master program student, and you will switch to one with thesis; I mean, it is not rocket science. "</p> <p>"Let's assume my advisor told me to meet up tomorrow to have dinner and let's also assume everyone in the class or in the session heard this. A classmate of mine can think 'Why did they invite him?' in fact, the professor who invited me out and I can understand this jealousy, we can both feel it. "</p> <p>"My close friends, with whom I studied for the graduate program admission examinations, are all in university now, but I still couldn't do it. Yes, this is jealousy, envy, you have just said, questioning self-efficacy; I am doing self-criticism now.</p> <p>"If there is anything to read, my peers are always ahead of for they have time, but I do not have much time. I am not sure whether it is called jealousy, but I have constantly upset myself in this situation saying 'maybe if you were not so busy, you could have studied as much as you wanted.' Metaphorically saying, as I was asleep, they made progress and yes, this is jealousy. "</p> <p>"Some postgraduate students are very talkative. They immediately express their ideas and are great at linking. One or two of my friends have such strengths, and they did not impress me much when I listened to them. An idea that many people liked was not very attractive to me, but some faculty members gave credit to those ideas, saying 'yes, it is a good idea.' I saw a close friend of mine; all his posts (on social media) were directed at a person. He writes about him. I was taken aback. He said, 'He is a doctorate student, so he may say whatever he wants. You should not be bothered by this'. They were both following each other (on social media), both were writing to each other indirectly; I was really surprised. "</p>
Jealousy in the context of a comparison between faculty members	<p>"Your advisor might be a little quieter in the institution, there may even be an elderly faculty member, somehow their students get more advantageous, have more opportunities, or this may be understood as such due to jealousy. Since I had a faculty member working in different fields, I felt I had been taken to a strange position, that I had become more disadvantaged as a student, and this came with jealousy."</p> <p>"The students of the professors in the periphery come together, and these conversations between us are unavoidable: 'I do not know whose student did this great thing, did you hear, we cannot do the same'".</p>

	<p>“In institutions where there is much competition, people feel lonely and there are groupings. To exemplify, there is a team, a professor, and they have good motivation. You cannot have that motivation when working with your advisor or supervisor, and there is a state of unhappiness. I don’t know whether it is jealousy or something else; a hostile atmosphere can arise. ”</p>
Jealousy in the context of academic publication	<p>"When you have a friend at an equal position to yours, with more academic publications, this question materializes in my mind: ‘Why didn't I have so many publications’ or ‘why can't I be successful, why don't I get involved in international connections like them?’ thinking that I had education in an institution with powerful international connections.</p> <p>“There are two examples that surprised me, one of them is my childhood friend. We are very close, and we have ties of kinship. He went abroad-to UK for his Ph.D. There were no Turkish publications about the topic of my thesis study, once I did some research, I saw that there were a few books merely in UK. I asked him to take the books, and I told him that I would pay for them. When he came, he did not bring any books. He was so close to me, and it was a huge disappointment. I know he could have brought these from the library; or easily transferred parts to a flash memory. At that moment, I thought, he is at a better point than me academically, and I am at a lower level. ”</p>
Jealousy in the context of managerial duty/promotion within the academy	<p>“We have heard ‘why does this academic can always establish such a relationship with the organization, why are they always in charge, or why are these people always assigned to the executive positions?’ These are maybe about academic jealousy.”</p>
Jealousy in the context of academic incentive	<p>" I notice the issue of academic encouragement has an effect on faculty because it is an inexorably economic issue. I say jealousy, but please do not visualize that the professors are at each other’s throats in front of the other professors; it is mostly verbal or implicative... "</p>
Jealousy in the context of the relatively wider academic environment	<p>“When collecting data, someone with the authority can reach out thousands of people with making a few phone calls. Such situations make me jealous. ”</p>
Jealousy in the context of favoritism by faculty members	<p>“When we were doing face-to-face education, two students of a professor in the department were assigned to more important tasks. They took over roles in symposiums held all over Türkiye. Later, they prepared oral presentations with their professor, again to be delivered in these symposiums. That professor made everything ready. ”</p>

The comments were on the ontological being of jealousy. Further, it was stressed jealousy was experienced in academic/scientific publication processes and in terms of managerial duty/promotion. Apart from these, it was underlined jealousy found a ground in academic incentive inducement or supplemental rewards, in the form of favoritism.

The Nature of Academic Jealousy

The third theme is "the nature of academic jealousy." The codes are: "jealousy in every sector/study environment/work environment," "competition depending on academic environment and conditions," and "experiencing jealousy in one's academic environment.". The participants' opinions, themes, and codes can be found in Table 4.

Table 4. The nature of academic jealousy

Codes	Opinions
Being jealous in every sector/study environment/work environment	<p>"I cannot say with absolute certainty whether jealousy is more evident in our area and I think it is not unique to us (the field of Educational Management)."</p> <p>"I remembered what the professor told me. Jealousy is a phenomenon/thing that exists in human nature."</p> <p>"Jealousy may be in there somewhere, and it is unpreventable. At first, I could not believe it was true. We think of academy, science, and studying as almost sacred things. Seeing this dark side of the matter, I say, 'these people are not robots, they can have weaknesses.'"</p> <p>" Just as it happens in higher academic positions, it takes place as part of gaining a master's degree, studying in an undergraduate program, at high school, and secondary school."</p>
Competition depends on the academic environment and conditions	"Frankly, I want to go abroad for my doctorate, and I cannot ignore the effect of the dynamics of the institution I am in."
Experiencing jealousy in his/her academic environment	"You are jealous of a person at your organization, but do not get jealous of a person you do not see around. This is nonsensical; you two are in the same field, striving for publications.".

Jealousy can take shape in the individual's academic environment and can be observed through academic competitions.

Consequences of Academic Jealousy

The fourth theme is "the results of academic jealousy." The sub-themes that came up with this theme are: "no academic jealousy," "in the positive direction," and "in the negative direction." Under the sub-theme of "no academic jealousy," "there was no one I would be jealous of academically" code; under the sub-theme of "positive," "experiencing academic jealousy around," "academic envy," "appreciating the academic achievements of friends" and "reacting to academic jealousy (greed, self-criticism, self-inquiry)" codes gathered and under the sub-theme of "negative," "feeling of failure due to academic jealousy," "feeling of injustice in academia," "harms of academic jealousy" and "exclusion due to academic competition" codes clustered. The participants' opinions, themes, and codes are shown in Table 5.

Table 5. Consequences of academic jealousy

Sub-Theme 1: No Academic Jealousy	Opinions
I have never had anyone around to be academically jealous of.	<p>"My peers were as humble as I am and having the title of doctor does not change them negatively, and since this would not change me either we may say there was no need to be jealous at all. "</p> <p>"Maybe I would have been jealous if I had attributed much meaning to earning degrees. To get the title of an associate professor, or professor should not be underestimated. These are things requiring effort, but it is not suitable for me to work too much."</p>
2. Sub-Theme: Positive Direction	
Experiencing academic jealousy around	Opinions "Should someone has publications, our goal is not to be better than them unlike what is the case with our close circle."
Academic envy	<p>"There is envy, jealousy, desire, and so on. How do we separate them? I see a professor's publications, and I say 'this professor has such good publications, I wish I could be like them' but at this point I have nothing negative against that professor, they are like a role model. I also say, 'I can do it too.' There is something positive here, something motivating."</p> <p>"There were people from other provinces commuting to attend courses and I could see they worked toward the courses more than I did. I had a desire to be like them."</p> <p>"I have friends who I think are more successful academically than me. They have worked harder than me. During the thesis stage, we went through the same stages; we experienced the same periods of indetermination, so to speak. I have a desire to be like them. We are being cooperative and this desire of mine did not affect our relationship adversely."</p> <p>" I am not jealous; on the contrary, my peers always encourage me and say, 'come on, let's finish this.' I want to be like them."</p>
Appreciating the academic achievements of friends	"My friends are ahead of me because they spend more time and labor. I admire them. Because they were exhausted, they devoted much time and worked hard. While they were making an effort, concentrating, and breaking a sweat, I was in a way sitting in the shade, so it would not be right to be jealous of them. "
Responding to academic jealousy (ambition, self-criticism, self-inquiry)	"My very close friends, whom I studied with toward the graduate degree, are all in university now, but I still could not do it; I am trying to achieve it. This feeds my determination and ambition."
3. Sub-Theme: Negative Direction	
Feeling of failure due to academic jealousy	<p>"Surely, our mental state changes occasionally. Sometimes we experience failures. "</p> <p>"I want to become a faculty so I need to work a lot, but I do not have time for this."</p>
Feeling of injustice in the academy	"Sometimes we say, 'it does not have anything to do with me; it is the other party's fault,' and think it is not fair ."
The harm of academic jealousy to people	"I think there is nothing you can go forward with, no matter how jealous you are, other than making your life miserable. If you are not already at peace with yourself, you will find something wrong in yourself and demotivate yourself. "
Exclusion due to academic competition	"I don't know if this is exclusion, but we did not see each other during the pandemic. "

Some evaluations signified there is no one to be jealous of in the environment. At the same time, it was spotlighted academic jealousy resulted in envy or desire, as self-criticism, and self-review. Bearing in mind academic jealousy causes a sense of failure and injustice on the part of the individual.

Fundamentals of Academic Jealousy

The fifth theme is "the foundations of academic jealousy." The codes are: "personality-academic jealousy relationship," "organizational culture-academic jealousy relationship," "age and workload-academic jealousy relationship," and "pre-adulthood-academic jealousy relationship." The participants' opinions, themes, and codes are communicated in Table 6.

Table 6. Fundamentals of academic jealousy

Codes	Opinions
Personality-academic jealousy relationship	<p>“People worldwide have amazing publications so how could I be jealous of these people here? So will I kick my friend down the ladder?”</p> <p>“...There is an organizational culture where people have positive and strong characters and through which their personalities are developed. When a new friend without any experience joins this environment, it turns out that this friend does not bring any of the negative behavior with them”.</p> <p>"Age and position are also very effective. When I started my master's degree at the age of 33, I was an administrator for 5-6 years then, we were 7-8 friends in a postgraduate program, I think we had a much more comfortable process by supporting each other without jealousy.”</p> <p>“I think it is a personal stance from the top management to the bottom. Some people want such things like wanting their names to appear first. I think it is entirely intrinsic and personal.”</p> <p>“Some people think others should be at lower levels to get to the top, they say, ‘the lower the people around me are, the higher I will be.’ So, they make a kind of relative evaluation. People want to be more successful, they want higher positions, titles, more money with projects, and they do not want others to do what they do because of their personality. ”</p>
The relationship between organizational culture and academic jealousy	<p>“I am a sociable person. Our field matches with my personal qualities. So, you need to talk, or you need to say something in your environment. When these two are together, a friend who does not speak or is inactive can develop the feeling of jealousy. I am trying to support them when I realize this. When we support each other, the system dissolves automatically, making the organization's culture a desired one.”</p> <p>“As new people enter into any organization, they bring a soul. They improve the quality of the organization. Then, the behaviors that we think is shallow, such as jealousy, are actually minimized.”</p>
Age and workload-academic jealousy relationship	<p>“Maturation and workload are prominent parameters germane to jealousy. I am 42 years old; I have 20 years of experience and I have worked as an administrator. You get enough of some things. Let alone being jealous of your other friend, you have to help each other because your workload is too much”.</p>
Pre-adulthood-academic jealousy relationship	<p>"Competing with each other, trying to be one step ahead, and preventing others from being successful are related to the early childhood period. I mean, it is something related to psychological factors. This is not something to do with the academy. Alternatively, it may be related to genes. "</p>

Academic jealousy has relevance to the individual's personality traits, the culture of the organization, age, and workload. Moreover, an association of academic jealousy with the pre-adulthood period was made.

Suggestions for Academic Jealousy

The sixth theme is "suggestions on academic jealousy." The codes are: "academic jealousy should be avoided," "academic jealousy should be recognized," and "academic success should be appreciated." The participants' opinions, themes, and codes are available in Table 7.

Table 7. Suggestions for academic jealousy

Codes	Opinions
Academic jealousy should be avoided	" Jealousy is not a virtuous behavior, and it is a bad thing to harm or block a person because of their success. "
The feeling of academic jealousy should be recognized	"The person should be fully aware of the feeling of jealousy. Unless they recognize it, they cannot cope with this emotion, which may have devastating consequences. If they are jealous of a person, what are the underlying reasons for being jealous? To give an instance, we may be jealous that they work hard, but we may also be jealous that they do things in a short time."
Academic achievement should be appreciated	"I wish my peers all the best, and I have never been jealous of them. I am proud of all. They became professors and reached a certain age. I never questioned myself, saying 'Why am I here?'. When the time comes, maybe I will be there. "

The participants made several suggestions in view of academic jealousy. They affirmed academic jealousy should be refrained from, being aware of whether one has this feeling is imperative and it is beneficial to appreciate achievements.

Discussion, Conclusion and Recommendations

The views on the phenomenon of "academic jealousy" clustered under six themes: "Factors affecting academic plans," "Academic jealousy in varying contexts," "The nature of academic jealousy," "The results of academic jealousy," "The basics of academic jealousy" and "Suggestions for academic jealousy."

Academic jealousy sometimes can be harmful both for the individual and the organization, and individuals can be omitted in case of academic competition. In this frame, academia as the centres of objective thinking, may turn out to be places of fierce competition that urge academics to ever-produce. In this direction, in the organizational understanding, competition, not appreciating but ignoring success, differences in terms of statuses, duties and roles, one's need to prove their power and negative organizational behaviors are triggers of academic jealousy. Jealousy manifests itself with anger and sadness caused by not having a feature or skill (Kocak, 2019). Since it is a response to the real or imaginary behavior of others (perpetrator), frequent or intense jealousy reactions highlight one's ability to manage and control the emotions of others (Bringle, 1981). Jealous individuals incline to developing a sense of inadequacy and may spread gossip and bully towards their successful co-workers. Jealousy threatens the overall well-being of the relevant organizations (Reyna, 2021). Academic jealousy facilitates rivalry in organizations (Bayar & Koca, 2021). In this research, academic jealousy can be observed in a similar fashion. Jealousy can indeed be a stimulator to enhance the performance of the individual (Sitinjak, 2016). That said, academic jealousy might cause mental problems in the long run, negatively impacting productivity, creativity, and enjoyment of relations in the work environment. Jealous individuals

are unhappy and restless and even quit their job (Ozdemir & Erdem, 2020). Jealousy then becomes a reason of personnel turn over concerning policy making. Jealousy reduces the meta-cognitive resources required for task goals, and impair achievement (Pekrun et al., 2002) and it can create tension, damage relationships, hinder communication, make teamwork less effective blocking well-being and peace of mind (Reyna, 2021). According to Cleary, Walter, Halcomb, and Lopez (2016), the embittered, hostile person can disrupt groups. Jealousy constitutes a salient concern of managers who are to establish and sustain a positive environment. On the other hand, jealousy can be inciting for the individual to achieve in an ironic fashion. This is because it is a positive trigger that requires an academic performance ironically (Sitinjak, 2016). Arguably, optimal academic jealousy can be useful to advance in the academic world.

Aydin-Kucuk and Tastan (2019) stress emotions are impulses with highly crucial effects. Employee jealousy can result in a loss of self-confidence (Ozdemir & Erdem, 2020) and may mean losing power (Bayar, and Koca, 2021). We unveiled academic jealousy can be a comparison and it is a result of this comparison (Aydin & Bozkurt, 2022; Sitinjak, 2016; Ozdemir, 2020). Negative events can cause anger, anxiety, jealousy to be reflected in the working environment (Ozdemir, 2021). Accordingly, mental health problems may result in jealousy in academia, which is already an arena or a quagmire (Reyna, 2021). Thinking about its rather paradoxical being, jealousy in academic organizations is a point that needs special attention. As there are plentiful points that boost jealousy (competition, ambition, career, promotion, comparison, individuality, hierarchy, and alike) it is too important to be ignored for the academic world (Ozdemir & Erdem, 2020).

Jealousy can eat up the individual (Bayar & Koca, 2021) since it is an unpleasant and destructive (Ozdemir & Erdem, 2020) as well as a social emotion (Leahy, 2020). We discovered jealousy is because of the extraordinary abilities of others like what is underpinned in the literature (Masse', and Gagne', 2015). Jealousy is found socially unacceptable (Cleary, Walter, Halcomb, & Lopez, 2016) and considered a topic should not be articulated.

There exist varying types of jealousy (Bayar & Koca, 2021) and success rankings lead to jealousy in the academic world (Bayar & Koca, 2021; Hudak, 2000). The competitive nature of academia is a fertile ground for the envy weeds to grow and multiply rapidly. These are factors specific to academia that create a challenging environment (Reyna, 2021). It was unearthed in this research that jealousy can be observed in academic/scientific publication phases which looks compatible with the literature.

The terms envy and jealousy are used interchangeably (Masse', and Gagne', 2015). These two can albeit be used differently (Bayar & Koca, 2021) and whereas the phenomenon of jealousy is accepted as a compound emotion, there is no consensus about its components (Hupka, 1984). Jealousy is a psychic phenomenon (Hudak, 2000). Envy is also expected to function as a means of informing the individual about their relatively inferior position (Rentzsch, Schröder-Abé & Schütz, 2015). Talking about envy in the workplace is really talking about a certain type of relationship between people (Hudak, 2000) and envy is expected to be a prominent factor underlying the self-esteem-hostility link, related to self-esteem (Rentzsch, Schröder-Abé & Schütz, 2015). In the world of academia, academics lacking self-esteem cannot warrant healthy role models for colleagues, and more importantly, for students.

Whilst envy involves the desire for something another has and implies a dual relationship, jealousy occurs in tripartite situations (Masse', and Gagne', 2015) and jealousy is always about three people; that is, jealousy encompasses the perception that a valuable relationship is threatened by a third party (Leahy, 2020).

Academic leaders should find ways to reduce jealousy by empowering members, making work more flexible promoting self-efficacy. They need to take individual psychological characteristics into account in their management style knowing when to intervene in team conflicts, create opportunities for learning, provide coaching and mentoring. Conflict resolution skills are necessary too (Reyna, 2021). One should also come up with positive ways of coping with emotions (Bringle, 1981). Academics should not waste time thinking about what others are doing. Instead, they should concentrate on topics to research and publish (Reyna, 2021). Jealousy can be managed creatively by claiming it, expressing gratitude to the envied good object, and compensating for the damaging emotion (Mouly & Sankaran, 2002). It is normal for human beings to compare themselves to others. But the truth is people come from different backgrounds. They have different experiences, abilities, programs, and strategies for self-regulation and motivation. A healthy way to look at the competition is to fight against personal limitations, not co-workers. Self-regulation strategies that can elevate productivity and success (Reyna, 2021). Jealousy is neither just good nor just bad and then eliminating all jealousy may not be meaningful (Bringle, 1981). Respect and concern for others, positive reinforcement, and open dialogue will be effective herbicide against envy weeds in academia. These key actions will help emerging researchers grow in a more supportive environment and minimize the devastating side effects of jealousy (Reyna, 2021).

Studies to scrutinize what of academic jealousy need to delve into its eminent dimensions: gender, department, country, resilience, as a purposeful act. Prospective studies can employ face to face interviews, mixed methods, and more participants using quantitative methods.

Conflict of Interest

There is no conflict of interest for the study.

Author Contributions

The first author: Conceptualization, Data Collection, Writing - Original Draft, Data Analysis

The second author: Data Collection, Writing - Review & Editing, Supervision of Findings

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